

“Comprehensive survey of parameters and dataset in predicting breast cancer: A systematic review of statistical and machine learning approaches”

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Abstract:

Breast cancer recurrence remains a significant clinical concern despite advances in early detection and treatment. Recurrence refers to return of cancer after a period of remission and can manifest locally, regionally or as distant metastases. Predicting recurrence is critical for improving patient outcomes and tailoring long-term management strategies. Multiple factors contribute to recurrence risk, including tumor size, histological grade, lymph node involvement, hormone receptor status, HER2 expression, molecular biomarkers such as Ki-67 and gene expression profiles. Additionally, patient adherence to treatment, type of therapy received and genetic predisposition play key roles. Recent developments in machine learning and genomics have improved recurrence prediction models, enabling more personalized approaches to care. However challenges remain in integrating clinical pathological and molecular data effectively. Ongoing research in recurrence mechanisms and predictive modelling is essential to reduce relapse rates and improve survival in breast cancer patients.

In this paper detailed survey on various parameters to be considered while predicting the recurrence time of breast cancer is done. The types of parameters include tumor pathology parameters. Biomarker and molecular parameters, patient and demographic factors.

Keywords: Breast cancer, recurrence time, factors for prediction, accuracy, machine learning algorithms.

1. Introduction:

Breast cancer is one of the most common life-threatening malignancies affecting women worldwide. It originates in the cells of the breast tissue, most commonly in the ducts or lobules. While it predominantly affects women, men can also develop breast cancer, albeit rarely^[1]. The disease is characterized by the uncontrolled growth of abnormal cells that can invade surrounding tissues and in advanced stages spread to distant parts of the body such as bones, lungs, liver and brain.

Early detection of breast cancer significantly improves the chances of successful treatments and survival. Key diagnostic tools include mammography, ultrasound, MRI, and biopsy, while treatment options vary based on cancer type, stage and biological markers. These options typically involve surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, hormonal therapy and targeted biological agents such as trastuzumab. Several factors contribute to the risk of recurrence. These include the initial tumor characteristics, molecular subtype and the type and completeness of treatment received. In recent years there has been growing interest in integrated machine learning and AI-driven models with clinical and genomic data to improve recurrence prediction.

2. Key parameters to predict breast cancer recurrence time after medication.

There are various key parameters to predict the recurrence time of breast cancer.

- a. **Demographic factors** play a significant role in predicting the risk of breast cancer recurrence. One of the most notable is age at diagnosis, with younger women particularly those under 35 to 40 years facing a higher risk of recurrence. This is largely attributed to the aggressive nature of tumors more commonly found in younger patients, such as high grade or triple negative subtypes which are less responsive to hormonal therapy^[2]. Menopausal status also influences recurrence risk, premenopausal women often have more biologically aggressive cancers and more prone to early recurrence compare to their post menopausal counterparts. Additionally race and ethnicity contribute to disparities in recurrence rates. Body mass index(BMI) is another critical factor obesity is linked to higher recurrence risk particularly in hormone receptor-positive cancers, due to increased estrogen production from adipose tissue, chronic inflammation and insulin resistance.^[3]
Lastly a family history of breast or ovarian cancer especially in first degree relatives, raises concern for hereditary syndromes such as BRCA mutations. These genetic alterations are associated with more aggressive disease phenotypes and higher recurrence potential. Together these demographic parameters provide valuable context for individualizing prognosis, tailoring treatment, and optimizing long term follow up strategies^[4].
- b. **Tumor characteristics** are among the most critical factors in predicting both the risk and timing of breast cancer. One of the primary features is tumor size. Larger tumors are associated with a higher probability of local or distant recurrence as they may have had more time to develop aggressive properties or to spread microscopically. Lymph node involvement is another strong prognostic marker; the presence and number of positive lymph nodes significantly increase the risk of recurrence. Particularly distant metastases^[5]. Patients with four or more involved nodes are considered high-risk and often require more aggressive systemic therapy. The histologic grade of the tumor ranging from low to high reflects how abnormal the cancer cells appear under the microscope and how quickly they are likely to grow. High grade tumors grow and spread faster and tend to recur earlier often within the first 23 years after treatment.
The hormone receptor status of the tumor is another key determinant. Estrogen receptor and progesterone receptor positive tumors tend to have a lower risk of early recurrence but are more prone to late recurrence even 10-20 years after initial treatment. In contrast ER/PR negative tumors particularly triple negative breast cancer which lack ER, PR and HER2 are more aggressive and tend to recur early usually within the first 3-5 years with a steep drop in recurrence risk thereafter.^[6]
Together these tumor specific characteristics are integral to risk stratification and guide decisions regarding adjuvant therapy follow up intensity and overall prognosis. They also help clinicians estimate when recurrence is most likely to occur whether in the early post treatment or after a longer disease-free interval.
- c. **Treatment related factors** are critical in predicting the recurrence of breast cancer as they directly influence the effectiveness of initial cancer control and long term disease management. One of the primary factors is the type of surgery performed, patients undergoing breast conserving surgery

typically require follow up radiation to reduce recurrence risk, where as mastectomy may be more appropriate for extensive disease. The use of adjuvant therapies such as chemotherapy, radiation, hormone therapy and targeted therapies also play a significant role. The timing, dosage and duration of these treatments as well as patient adherence strongly affect outcomes. For instance studies show that failing to complete full course of hormone therapy significantly increases the likelihood of recurrence in hormone receptor-positive patients. Moreover delays in initiating adjuvant therapies after surgery have been associated with higher recurrence rates. Finally treatment related toxicity may lead to dose reductions or early discontinuation which can compromise treatment efficacy.

- d. Follow up and prognostic indicators** are essential components in predicting the timing and likelihood of breast cancer^[8]. After initial treatment regular follow up care is crucial for early detection of recurrence , monitoring treatment effects and managing long term complication. This typically includes periodic physical exams, mammography, imaging studies, and in some cases blood test for tumor marker like CA 15-3 or CEA. The frequency and type follow up are often individualized based on the patients initial cancer stage, biological subtype and response to treatment. Prognostic indicators provide insights into the biological behavior of the tumor and help estimate recurrence risk. Key indicators include tumor size , lymph node involvement , histological grade and molecular markers^[12].

Table 2.1 Key Parameters

Ref No	Name of Parameters	Variables of parameters
1.	Tumor pathology parameters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tumor size • Tumor grade • Lymph node involvement • Lymphovascular invasion • Histological subtype
2.	Biomarker and Molecular Parameters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estrogen receptor • Progesterone receptor • HER2 status • Ki-67 index • BRCA1/ BRCA2 mutations
3.	Treatment related Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of Surgery performed • Radiotherapy • Chemotherapy regimen • Hormonal therapy

3. Public datasets available for predicting the recurrence time of breast cancer.

- a. The METABRIC (molecular taxonomy of breast cancer international consortium) dataset is a comprehensive resource that integrates genomic, transcriptomic, and clinical data from over 2500 primary breast cancer tumors. Collected from five centers in the united kingdom and Canada, this dataset aims to

4.	Patient and Demographic Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age at diagnosis • Menopausal status • Comorbidities • Body mass index • Smoking and alcohol consumption • Genetic predisposition
5.	Follow up and monitoring indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time to recurrence • Adherence to follow up visits and imaging • Surveillance imaging
6.	Optimal but emerging factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circulating tumor DNA • Immune profile

provide a detailed understanding of breast cancer subtypes and their molecular characteristics. Researchers can access the METABRIC dataset through platforms like cBioPortal and Synapse, which provide tools for data visualization exploration and analysis^[14]. The dataset has been instrumental in identifying novel cancer genes.

b. The TCGA-BRCA (the cancer genome at last breast invasive carcinoma) dataset is a comprehensive and publicly accessible resource that provides a multidimensional view of the breast cancer biology. Initiated by the national cancer institute and the national human genome research institute, TCGA-BRCA encompasses data from over 1000 primary breast cancer samples, integrating clinical, genomic, transcriptomic, epigenomic, and proteomic information^[15]. This extensive dataset enables researchers to explore the molecular underpinnings of breast cancer and identify potential therapeutic targets.

c. The breast cancer Wisconsin dataset available through the UCI machine learning repository is a widely utilized resource in the field of machine learning repository classification tasks. It compares 569 instances, each characterized by 30 numerical features derived from digitized images of the fine needle aspirants of breast masses. The features describes various attributes of cell nuclei present in the images such as radius, textures, perimeter, area, smoothness, compactness, concavity. The data set is labeled with 2 classes: M for malignant and B for benign tumors. The primary objective is to classify tumors as malignant or benign based on these features, making it a valuable tool for developing and evaluating diagnostic models^[16].

4. Prediction algorithms

The prediction of breast cancer recurrence through machine learning has the potential to significantly improve patient outcomes by enabling early interventions and personalized treatment strategies. The choice of the algorithm depends on the trade off between accuracy and interpretability, with high performance model such as SVMs, ANNs, Random forest leading the way. However for practical clinical applications models that are both effective and interpretable like Logistic Regression and Decision trees may be preferred for their transparency and ease of integration into healthcare systems^[17].

Table 4.1 Prediction Algorithms

Ref No	Algorithm	Accuracy(%)	Dataset used
1.	Support Vector Machine	98.5	Breast cancer Wisconsin diagnostic
2.	Artificial Neural Network	97.85	Various datasets
3.	Random forest	95.32.	Wisconsin breast cancer diagnostic
4.	Logistic Regression	96.02	Wisconsin breast cancer diagnostic
5.	Decision tree	94.15	Wisconsin breast cancer diagnostic
6.	K-Nearest Neighbors(KNN)	94.0	Wisconsin breast cancer diagnostic

6. Conclusion

Breast cancer is a heterogeneous disease and accurate prognosis and treatment depend on the careful evaluation of a wide range of parameters. These factors help define tumor biology, guide treatment decisions and predict outcomes such as recurrence of survival. Integrating traditional clinical data with molecular and genomic insights enables precision medicine approaches for breast cancer care.

References:

- [1] M. S. Yarabarla, L. K. Ravi and A. Sivasangari, "Breast Cancer Prediction via Machine Learning," 2019 3rd International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI), Tirunelveli, India, 2019, pp. 121-124, doi: 10.1109/ICOEI.2019.8862533.
- [2] A. Chauhan, H. Kharpate, Y. Narekar, S. Gulhane, T. Virulkar and Y. Hedau, "Breast Cancer Detection and Prediction using Machine Learning," 2021 Third International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA), Coimbatore, India, 2021, pp. 1135-1143, doi: 10.1109/ICIRCA51532.2021.9544687.
- [3] Y. Wankhade, S. Toutam, K. Thakre, K. Kalbande and P. Thakre, "Machine Learning Approach for Breast Cancer Prediction: A Review," 2023 2nd International Conference on Applied Artificial Intelligence and Computing (ICAAIC), Salem, India, 2023, pp. 566-570, doi: 10.1109/ICAAIC56838.2023.10141164
- [4] A. Allada, G. R. K. Rao, P. Chitturi, H. Chindu, M. S. N. Prasad and P. Tatineni, "Breast Cancer Prediction using Deep Learning Techniques," 2021 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Smart Systems (ICAIS), Coimbatore, India, 2021, pp. 306-311, doi: 10.1109/ICAIS50930.2021.9395793.
- [5] C. Bista, A. M. S. Slimanzay, M. S. Sheikh and P. Srinivasa Rao, "Breast Cancer Prediction System Utilizing Machine Learning Algorithms," 2024 IEEE AITU: Digital Generation, Astana, Kazakhstan, 2024, pp. 80-84, doi: 10.1109/IEEECONF61558.2024.10585589
- [6] M. P. Behera, A. Sarangi, D. Mishra and S. K. Sarangi, "Breast Cancer Prediction Using Long Short-Term Memory Algorithm," 2022 5th International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Networks (CINE), Bhubaneswar, India, 2022, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/CINE56307.2022.10037258
- [7] B. S., M. A. M. J., P. B. N., S. F. P. and K. A., "Breast Cancer Classification and Recurrence Prediction Using Artificial Neural Networks and Machine Learning Techniques," 2023 Second International Conference on Electrical, Electronics, Information and Communication Technologies (ICEEICT), Trichirappalli, India, 2023, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICEEICT56924.2023.10157890

- [8] A. I. Pritom, M. A. R. Munshi, S. A. Sabab and S. Shihab, "Predicting breast cancer recurrence using effective classification and feature selection technique," 2016 19th International Conference on Computer and Information Technology (ICCIT), Dhaka, Bangladesh, 2016, pp. 310-314, doi: 10.1109/ICCITECHN.2016.7860215
- [9] Priyanka, Kumar Sanjeev. "A review paper on breast cancer detection using deep learning." *IOP conference series: materials science and engineering*. Vol. 1022. No. 1. IOP Publishing, 2021.
- [10] Rautela, Kamakshi, Dinesh Kumar, and Vijay Kumar. "A systematic review on breast cancer detection using deep learning techniques." *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering* 29.7 (2022): 4599-4629.
- [11] Rautela, Kamakshi, Dinesh Kumar, and Vijay Kumar. "A systematic review on breast cancer detection using deep learning techniques." *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering* 29.7 (2022): 4599-4629.
- [12] Gami, Bhavin, Khushi Chauhan, and Brijeshkumar Y. Panchal. "Breast cancer detection using deep learning." *Mobile Radio Communications and 5G Networks: Proceedings of Third MRCN 2022*. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, 2023. 85-95.
- [13] Mohamed, Ammar, et al. "The impact of data processing and ensemble on breast cancer detection using deep learning." *Journal of Computing and Communication* 1.1 (2022): 27-37.
- [14] Tsietsos, Dennies, Abid Yahya, and Ravi Samikannu. "A review on thermal imaging-based breast cancer detection using deep learning." *Mobile Information Systems* 2022.1 (2022): 8952849.
- [15] Thaseen, Aliya, et al. "Breast cancer detection using deep learning model." *Proceedings of Third International Conference on Advances in Computer Engineering and Communication Systems: ICACECS 2022*. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, 2023.
- [16] Dedeepya, Parvathaneni, Abel Jaba Deva Krupa, and Samiappan Dhanalakshmi. "A comparative analysis on various machine learning techniques for breast cancer detection." *2023 International Conference on Intelligent Systems for Communication, IoT and Security (ICISCoIS)*. IEEE, 2023.
- [17] Zeid, Magdy Abd-Elghany, Khaled El-Bahnasy, and S. E. Abo-Youssef. "DeepBreast: Building Optimized Framework for Prognosis of Breast Cancer Classification Based on Computational Intelligence." *2022 2nd International Mobile, Intelligent, and Ubiquitous Computing Conference (MIUCC)*. IEEE, 2022.
- [18] Ahmad, Ghulab Nabi, et al. "Comparative study of optimum medical diagnosis of human heart disease using machine learning technique with and without sequential feature selection." *IEEE Access* 10 (2022): 23808-23828.
- [19] S. Kabiraj, L. Akter, M. Raihan, N. J. Diba, E. Podder and M. M. Hassan, "Prediction of Recurrence and Nonrecurrence Events of Breast Cancer using Bagging Algorithm," 2020 11th International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT), Kharagpur, India, 2020, pp. 1- 5, doi: 10.1109/ICCCNT49239.2020.9225440.
- [20] R. Kumar, M. Chaudhry, H. K. Patel, N. Prakash, A. Dogra and S. Kumar, "An Analysis of Ensemble Machine Learning Algorithms for Breast Cancer Detection: Performance and Generalization," 2024 11th International Conference on Computing for Sustainable Global Development (INDIACom), New Delhi, India, 2024, pp. 366-370, doi: 10.23919/INDIACom61295.2024.10498618
- [21] Hasan, Srwa & Sagheer, Ali , Veisi, Hadi. (2021). Breast Cancer Classification Using Machine Learning Techniques: A Review. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*. 12. 1970- 1979.
- [22] Dubey, Chhaya & Shukla, Nidhi & Kumar, Dharmendra Singh, Ashutosh & Dwivedi, Vijay. (2022). Breast Cancer Modeling and Prediction Combining Machine Learning and Artificial Neural Network Approaches. 119-124. 10.1109/ICCCIS56430.2022.10037709.
- [23] Bista, Chirayou M, Asreetha ,Slimanzay, Salahuddin Sheikh, Md & Rao, P. (2024). Breast Cancer Prediction System Utilizing Machine Learning Algorithms. 80-84. 10.1109/IEEECONF61558.2024.10585589.
- [24] Nathiya, S. & Sumitha, J.. (2021). A Comparative Study on Breast Cancer Prediction using Optimized Algorithms. 1401-1405. 10.1109/ICOSEC51865.2021.9591787. [7] Raihan, M.. (2020). Breast Cancer Risk Prediction using XGBoost and Random Forest Algorithm. 10.1109/ICCCNT49239.2020.9225451.

- [25] Choudhari, Gauri , Desai, Rutuja , Dagale, Pratik , Dashetwar, Isha. (2023). Breast Cancer Prediction Using Various Machine Learning Algorithms and Their Comparative Analysis. 1-6. 10.1109/PuneCon58714.2023.10450082.
- [26] Hegde, Harshita Kodipalli, Ashwini. (2022). Machine Learning Based Approach for Breast Cancer Detection. 782-786. 10.1109/ICCCIS56430.2022.10037645.
- [27] Aditya, Jatin. (2021). Optimized Ensemble Prediction Model for Breast Cancer. 1-4. 10.1109/ITSSIoE53029.2021.9615269.
- [28] Rovshenov, Atajan, Peker, Serhat. (2022). Performance Comparison of Different Machine Learning Techniques for Early Prediction of Breast Cancer using Wisconsin Breast Cancer Dataset. 1-6. 10.1109/IISEC56263.2022.9998248.
- [29] Yifeng, Dou , Jinsong, Lv , Wentao, Meng. (2024). Study on Breast Cancer Classification Prediction based on XGBoost. 411-416. 10.1109/IMCEC59810.2024.10575645.
- [30] Egwom, Onyinyechi , Hamada, Mohamed , Yusuf, Saratu , Hassan, Mohammed. (2021). The Role of Linear Discriminant Analysis for Accurate Prediction of Breast Cancer. 340-344. 10.1109/MCSoc51149.2021.00057.
- [31] Kaur, Arpanpreet ,Gupta, Sheifali. (2024). Unveiling Precision in Breast Cancer Prediction with Random Forest and Decision Trees. 1232-1236. 10.1109/ICOSEC61587.2024.10722493.
- [32] B. S., M. A. M. J., P. B. N., S. F. P. and K. A., "Breast Cancer Classification and Recurrence Prediction Using Artificial Neural Networks and Machine Learning Techniques," 2023 Second International Conference on Electrical, Electronics, Information and Communication Technologies (ICEEICT), Trichirappalli, India, 2023, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICEEICT56924.2023.10157890.
- [33] Prem Kumar, Josephine. (2020). Identification of Factors Causing Breast Cancer using Factor Analysis. International Journal of Engineering Research and. V9. 10.17577/IJERTV9IS020031.